

Proof of Millennium Theorem "P versus NP"

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Abstract. We go on towards the proof of concept of Millennium Theorem proposed by Stephen Cook, we state that polynomial classes and its successors like non-polynomial (NP) are equal along the function equilibrium which is justified by the parallel processing law, we will also give the exact algorithm to Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) which is computed in the polynomial complexity time of the product of linear and logarithmic operands, the linear algorithm for the maximum flow problem is also given. In this short paper we give the notion of the equivalence of the complexity classes due to the recent research according to Rabin-Scott subset construction. We will also give a notion to the famous "X+Y Problem" which can be solved efficiently in quadratic polynomial time on the dual deterministic Turing machine, for which the general definition is also given.

Keywords: computational complexity, P versus NP, P = NP, proof.

Pre-historical facts. We discuss the main statement and proof made by author of "P versus NP" theorem Stephen Cook - a winner of Alan Mathison Turing Award sponsored by Association of Computing Machinery (ACM). In this notable works [1, 2, 3, 4] he first proofs the existence of unsolvable problems along the divided complexity classes known as polynomial (P) which can be solved in the observed amount of time and non-polynomial (NP) which cannot be solved using the approaches developed up to the present time in the fixed time complexity. There and onwards this question was raised for more than decades and still remains actual up to the present time. We will show further that practical algorithms exist which solve the NP-hard problem in a meaningful time span on any type of automata using an algorithmic approach. We will show the proof of concept by proposing first the algorithm to the classical Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) and a linear algorithm to the maximum flow problem [5].

We prove the above fact by the assumption already given in the statement before: thus, as we know any non-deterministic finite automata (NFA) can be converted to analogous deterministic finite automata (DFA) [6].

According to our latest research the subset construction is P-complete [7] and, thus, there exist no automata with the strict property given above, thus, it follows that $P = NP$.

Thus, Klaus Schneider's canonical forms appear almost [8] in any case of in-state minimization and conversion of NFA to DFA via subset construction and, thus, can be replaced by the deterministic turing machine by implying the free parameter-like position in the automata.

Traveling Salesman Problem in almost linear time. From the proof of equivalence of complexity classes it follows that there is a logarithmic-linear algorithm for TSP. We describe this algorithm in a few steps by using the classical Dijkstra approach of finding the shortest path in a connected graph. As the algorithms both are similar, they still have significant differences as for TSP we define the following method of solving this problem in

$O(n \cdot \log(n))$: start from the empty set of paths, connect the paths by finding the shortest edge from finish to the start of this path if it doesn't form the cycle, repeat these steps until we get the full Hamiltonian cycle and path.

We're using a simple threading approach when each of the paths is merged on the fly during the simulation of moving travelers as if they would be put on each of the starting vertices.

Proof of $P = NP$. As we have devised the subset of problems strictly in NP and not in P, we know that subset construction is still P-complete with respect to the pre-defined canonical forms as it was shown before in [7].

We can only conclude that such forms always lead to the polynomial size equivalent DFA to the source NFA for which the powerset, or subset construction is to be applied in order to get the full state space which is aware of handling the same result without permitting the famous halt problem.

Thus, as we have defined that problems lying strictly in NP-class are executed deterministically with the same time complexity as P-problems we can conclude that this set is empty, which leads to the strict outcome like P equals NP, or $P = NP$.

For more convenience in the equivalence of P and NP classes as the result of the emptiness of the strict NP-classes of problems, we adjust our argument by building the simple deterministic position automata for the typically parametrized decision problem. This decision problem is approximated by the free parameter which is decreased each time it passes the fragment of built automata where typical logic fails due to the harder representation and re-interpretation of subset construction. We give it a new look and feel with the powerful parametric building which is widely known in the methodology known as "on the fly construction" which was well deployed in software packages like PCRE [9].

By parameterizing the size of the input clause in the source pattern, we omit the whole logic of automata to be applied which leads to the exponential growth of the reduction spaces which combine the simple logic of regular languages which are recognized by the Turing machine. This technique is novelistic as it wasn't applied before in problems where the time and space is crucial as we use it for the strict proof as an outcome of $P = NP$.

Indeed, Stephen Cook in his last message to the computer scientists' community [1], proposed that there will be wide horizons of the future built on the assumption that intractable problems could be solved efficiently using mathematical optimization methods like simplex [10]. Indeed, the intractable problems operate only on polynomial space within the non-existent gap of the strictly NP-aware problems, which are resolved by the Schneider-Rabin-Scott theorem of the subset construction being not so "state explosive" as it was meant and opposed before by many researchers as well as many public sources of discussing this question in-depth.

"X+Y" Problem. The dual Turing machines for which we built the full sparse set after sorting both sequences in increasing order can emit a single element each time and then return to the observed state where each row and each column are strictly ordered according to the relation between numbers in sequences and their derived sums. This gives the quadratic solution to the problem which is less in magnitude than the logarithmic, for this fact it can make it more practical.

Meanwhile, dual deterministic Turing Machines, or DDDFA, are operated on the matrix rather than a vector tape.

Maximum Flow in linear time. The linear time complexity for the classical network flow problem follows from the algorithm which can be solved in a few steps by introducing the weight potential method which includes the first step as forming the possible paths along the accumulated potential and minimal from the incoming and outgoing flow for the source and sink of the path along the network - the latter step is to compute the potential for each vertex in a flow. This gives the linear complexity and, thus, makes this problem practical which can be used in simulating the natural processes along the user-defined hardware devices which operate on this standard basis.

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Conclusion. The common misinterpretation of the "P versus NP" theorem lies between the fact that it can be solved effectively, still, it doesn't follow that from this consequence we can devise the relationship between two classes. We give the notion of non-existence of the problem lying in-between NP and P classes of complexity which are definitely to be operated on non-deterministic Turing machines, or NFA, and deterministic Turing machines, or DFA. Thus, there's no difference between deterministic and non-deterministic approach which is replaced by the deterministic parameterized search and there's no difference between this two approaches as problem always lies inside the deterministic Turing machine and the polynomial class of complexity - as we have shown above there's nothing which will lead to the different scenario.

We have also developed stable and minimal in complexity time solutions for the Traveling Salesman Problem and Maximum Flow Problem - which results from the proof of the functional conjecture of the complexity classes along the equivalence function of P and NP. The further steps are to find other polynomial solutions for the problems which weren't practically before.

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